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Impact of Oil Revenue and Exchange Rate Fluctuation on Economic Growth in Nigeria (1981-2015)

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the trend of the exchange rate, oil revenue and economic growth, in Nigeria from 1981 to 2015. This research also seeks to determine the impact of exchange rate fluctuations and oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria on the basis of annual data from 1981 to 2015. Secondary data was used in this study from 1981 to 2015. Relevant data for the study was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria's statistical bulletin (2015) and World Development Indicators WDI (2015). Trends and an OLS (Ordinary

Least Square) estimation technique were used to analyse the various objectives of the study. The study employed both Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Philips Perron (PP) unit root test, and Ordinary Least Square regression technique. Results of ADF and PP tests show evidence of unit root in the data.

The study reveals that the exchange rate (ER) is negative and statistically insignificant. The oil revenue ratio (OR) is positive and statistically significant in model 1, but became negative and statistically insignificant in model 2. The interaction between the ER and OR ratios is positive and statistically significant in model 2. Given the positive value of the interaction variable, this study concludes that both ER and OR play a complementary role in Nigeria's economic growth and that oil revenue is constrained by the exchange rate. The study however recommended diversification of export based revenue as a means of minimizing the over reliance of government revenue on crude oil and petroleum products, which will in turn encourage emerging entrepreneurs to develop new areas of production promoting employment, economic growth and development.

Keywords: Economic Growth, Exchange Rate Fluctuations, Oil Revenue.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent times, the Nigerian economy has struggled with fluctuations in its exchange rate, coupled with an outrageous decrease in the revenue accruing to the federal government from crude oil sales, which have resulted in a recession in the economy. The exchange rate can be defined as the value of a nation's currency when converting to another currency. Exchange rates determine the relative prices of domestic and foreign goods, as well as the strength of the external sector's participation in international trade. The exchange rate of an economy has a crucial role to play, as it directly affects all the macroeconomic variables such as: domestic price indicator, profitability of traded goods and services, allocation of resources and investment decisions, which explains why the monetary authorities and private sectors seek stability in this variable (Ajakaiye 2001). As noted by

Ewa, (2011), the exchange rate of the naira was relatively stable between 1973 and 1979 during the oil boom era, and when agricultural products accounted for more than 70% of the nation's gross domestic product (GDP). In 1986, when federal government adopted the Structural Adjustment Policy (SAP), the country moved from a peg regime to a flexible exchange rate regime, where the exchange rate was left completely, to be determined by market forces, but rather the prevailing system is the managed float whereby monetary authorities intervene periodically in the foreign exchange market in order to attain some strategic objectives (Mordi 2006).

According to Obadan (2006), as cited in Augustine (2015:1), "Oil is an international trade commodity that attracts foreign exchange and is a quick source of capital accumulation. Huge revenues are realised from the wide differential between unit production costs and economic rents, royalties, petroleum taxes, and oil exports." With the neglect of the real sector of the economy due to the discovery of oil, there has been a downturn in economic performance, coupled with other institutional difficulties that impede the growth possibilities of the economy.

Since the discovery of oil in commercial quantities in 1970s, oil revenue has been, and still is, the mainstay of the Nigerian economy. Nigeria has neglected her strong agriculture and light manufacturing bases in favour of an unhealthy dependence on crude oil. Oil wealth has led to a concurrent decline of other sectors in the economy and has fuelled massive migration to cities leading to increasingly wide spread poverty, especially in rural areas. As a result, Nigeria's job market has witnessed very high degrees of unemployment, small wages and pitiable working environments (Adedipe 2004). Between 1970 to 2000 Nigeria's poverty rate increased from 36 percent to just under 70 percent, and it is believed that oil revenue did not seem to add to the standard of living at this time, but actually caused it to decline (Martin & Subramanian, 2003).

In the words of Englama, Duke, Ogunleye and Isma'il (2010), as crude oil became an export commodity in Nigeria in 1958, following the discovery of the first producible well in 1956, the contribution of oil to the federal government revenue rose from 26.3 percent in 1970 to 82.1 percent in 1974, and in 2008 oil revenue constituted 83 percent of the federal government revenue, largely on account of an increase in oil prices in the international market. The gigantic rise in oil revenue was caused by the Middle East war of 1973. It created extraordinary, surprising, and unforeseen wealth for Nigeria and the naira appreciated as foreign exchange influxes offset outflows and Nigeria foreign reserves increased (Adedipe 2004).

The value of Nigeria's total export revenue in 2010 stood at US\$70,579 million, while income from petroleum exports of the total export revenue was US\$61,804 million, representing about 87.6 percent. The absolute dependence on oil export revenue has accentuated the level of Nigeria's economy vulnerability to sudden movements in the oil price. The failure of government to channel the surplus successfully from the oil sector to other sectors of the economy, placed the economy at the mercy of fluctuations in oil revenue, as a decrease in oil revenue will in turn imply a decrease in government revenue. Thus a decline in oil revenue and the consequences meant that the Nigerian government could no longer finance its expenditures, since the foreign reserve which was expected to serve as a shock absorber became depleted over time, with the economy having nothing to fall back on.

As a result of the development in the oil sector, in 1970's the share of agriculture in total exports declined significantly, while that of oil increased. However, from 1981 the world oil market started to deteriorate, thus affecting the Nigerian economy because of the country's dependence on oil sales from her export earnings. As such, a decline in oil price implies a decline in her export earnings, which will also have an effect on the exchange rate and oil revenue.

However, although only a few studies have been carried out on this issue, some authors combined the oil price shock and exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth in Nigeria (Matthew & Adegboye, 2014; Augustine 2015; Shehu 2009), oil revenue and economic growth (Ibeh, 2013; Ogbonna, 2012; Christian & Teymur, 2014, etc.), exchange rate fluctuations and economic growth (Amassoma & Odeniyi, 2016; Ismaila, 2016; Adeniran, Yusuf, & Adeyemi, 2014, etc.), while to the best knowledge of the researcher, no existing study has successfully combined the oil revenue and exchange rate fluctuations. Rather, they made use of the oil price shock and exchange rate fluctuations. Shehu (2009), Augustine (2015), and Mathew and Adegboye (2014), all worked on the effect of oil price shock and exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth in Nigeria, of which they all found out that the oil price shock and appreciation in the level of exchange rate exerted a positive impact on real economic growth in Nigeria.

All the authors mentioned above arrived at similar conclusions, since they have all considered the issue from a similar direction (oil price and exchange rate fluctuations), with none looking at the effect of oil revenue rather than the oil price. As oil revenue constitutes the bulk of government revenue in Nigeria, it becomes more appropriate, as it is more directly related to economic performance than the oil price, which is not a clear representation of the contribution of the oil sector to the economy. Thus arises the need to not just examine the effects of the oil price and exchange rate fluctuations on the Nigerian economy, but rather to examine the impact of oil revenue and exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth in Nigeria, as this will help show the relative and joint impact of changes in oil revenue and exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

An immense number of researchers have conducted (both foreign and indigenous) research studies on the oil price shock and exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth (Matthew & Adegboye, 2014; Augustine

2015; Shehu 2009), oil revenue and economic growth (Ibeh, 2013; Ogbonna, 2012; Christian & Teymur, 2014), exchange rate fluctuations and economic growth (Amassoma & Odeniyi, 2016; Ismaila, 2016; Adeniran, Yusuf, & Adeyemi, 2014). Some of these authors and their researchers are reviewed in this study. The study would be divided into three categories.

2.1 Oil price shock and exchange rate fluctuations on economic growth

Matthew and Adegboye (2014) examined the effect of the oil price shock and exchange rate instability on economic growth in Nigeria from 1986 to 2012. Time series quarterly data was used to examine the nature of causality among the variables. The Johansen VAR-based cointegration technique was applied to examine the sensitivity of real economic growth to changes in oil prices and real exchange rate volatility in the long-run, while the short run dynamics were checked using a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The Granger pairwise causality test revealed unidirectional causality from oil prices to real gross domestic product (GDP). The findings of the paper show that oil price shock and appreciation in the level of an exchange rate, exert a positive impact on real economic growth in Nigeria. It recommends greater diversification of the economy through investment in key productive sectors of the economy to guard against the vicissitude of oil price shock and exchange rate volatility.

Shehu (2009) investigated the impact of the oil price shock and exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria from 1986 to 2007 using quarterly data. The Johansen VAR-based cointegration technique was applied to examine the sensitivity of real economic growth to changes in oil prices and real exchange rate volatility in the long-run, while the short run dynamics was checked using a vector error correction model. The Granger pairwise causality test revealed unidirectional causality from oil prices to real GDP and bidirectional causality from real exchange rate to real GDP and vice versa. Findings of the research paper further showed that the oil price shock and an appreciation in the level of the exchange rate, exerts a positive

impact on real economic growth in Nigeria. The study also recommended greater diversification of the economy through investment in key productive sectors of the economy to guard against the vicissitude of oil price shock and exchange rate volatility.

Augustine (2015) analysed exchange rate fluctuations, the oil price and economic performance as well as examining empirical evidence from Nigeria from 1960 to 2013. The study probed the nexus and the magnitude of the effects of fluctuation in the exchange rate on oil price and on how it impacts the Nigeria's economic performance. Against this background, the study simultaneously evaluated the effects of exchange rate fluctuations on crude oil prices, as well as on economic performance. The ordinary least square and the two stage least squares estimation techniques were employed. Also, in order to examine the time series properties of the data, the study employed the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) method since the Engle–Granger single equation cointegration test is based upon the ADF test. The study found that real exchange rates have a positive effect on Nigeria's economic performance. The author also found that a 1% increase in the price of oil would positively influence the economic performance of Nigeria by a magnitude of 4%. Therefore, the author concluded that the real exchange rate has a negative effect on the oil price and a positive effect on economic performance. To promote a sound economic policy capable of fast tracking development, the study recommends that the government should diversify the economy through judicious investment in the real sector, so as to guide the economy against external shocks such as the international oil price.

2.2 Oil revenue and economic growth

Ibeh (2013) investigated the impact of oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. (1980-2010). The ordinary least square (OLS) regression technique was employed. Considering the impact of time on changes in economic variables, the analysis was carried out using the simple regression method in which the gross domestic product (GDP), proxy for economic growth was

used as the dependent variable, while the oil revenue (OREV) and time appeared as repressors. The researcher however found a positive, significant relationship between oil revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. The paper recommended that there is a need to develop the agricultural sector side by side with the oil sector, because oil is a wasting asset and too much reliance on oil to the neglect of agriculture is not of much benefit to the economy. Through this means, the industry sector will be modernised through the transfer of resources from the agricultural sector.

Ogbonna (2012) examined petroleum income and the Nigerian economy: empirical evidence, from 2000 to 2009 using the Gross domestic product (GDP), per capita income (PCI), and inflation (INF) as the explained variables, and oil revenue, petroleum profit tax/royalties (PPT/R), and licensing fees (LF) as the explanatory variables. The sample covers all the economic sectors of the country, including the oil sector and the non-oil sectors. Simple regressions models were used in this study to evaluate the data collected. The results show that the oil revenue has a positive and significant relationship with GDP and PCI, but a positive and insignificant relationship with INF. Similarly, PPT/R has a positive and significant relationship with GDP and PCI, but a negative and insignificant relationship with inflation. It was also found that LF has a positive but insignificant relationship between GDP, PCI and INF, respectively. Based on these findings, this study concludes that petroleum income (oil revenue and PPT/R) has positively and significantly impacted the Nigerian economy when measured by GDP and PCI for the period 2000 to 2009. The conclusion therefore supports the opinions of previous studies that income from a nation's natural resources (e.g. petroleum) has a positive influence on economic growth and development. It is important to note that of the three independent variables (oil revenue, petroleum profit tax/royalty, and licensing fees), oil revenue and petroleum profit tax/royalty showed a more robust significant, positive effect on the explained variables (GDP, PCI and INF) that measure growth and development in the Nigerian economy.

Christian and Teymur (2014) examine the impact of oil revenue on the Iranian economy and the Gulf States. In line with the neoclassical growth model, a persistent stream of oil revenues might have a long lasting impact on GDP per capita in oil exporting countries through higher investment activities. This relationship is explored for Iran and the countries of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) using (panel) cointegration techniques. For Iran, the series covered the period 1965-2012. For comparison, the post-revolutionary period (1980-2012) is considered separately. The sample period is 1980-2012 for the Gulf countries. The existence of cointegration between oil revenues, GDP and investment can be confirmed for all countries. While the cointegration vector is found to be unique for Iran, long run equations for GDP and investment per capita are distinguished for the Gulf countries. Both variables respond to deviations from the steady state, while oil income can be treated as weakly exogenous. The long run oil elasticities for the Gulf States exceed their Iranian counterparts. In addition, investment in Iran does not react to oil revenues in the long run. Hence, oil revenues may have been spent less wisely in Iran over the past decades.

2.3 Exchange rate fluctuations and economic growth

Amassoma and Odeniyi (2016) examined the nexus between exchange rate variation and economic growth in Nigeria, using annual data of forty-three (43) years covering the period (1970 – 2013). The standard deviation method was employed to capture and estimate the fluctuation inherent in the model as regards the research's objective. The study employed econometric techniques such as; Multiple Regression Model, Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test, Johansen Cointegration test and the Error Correction Model (ECM). Evidence from the study exhibited that there exists a positive but insignificant impact of exchange rate fluctuation on Nigerian economic growth in both the long run and short run. This result is attributed to the ability of the Nigerian government to effectively regulate some other important macroeconomic variables which can negatively influence the

exchange rate, which has thereby helped curtail the effects of exchange rate fluctuation during the study period. This is an indication that monetary authorities might have initiated policies that helped absorb the influence of exchange rate fluctuation on economic growth in Nigeria. Therefore, the paper recommended that the government should encourage domestic production of goods and services for naira exchange rate appreciation and generally promote economic growth in Nigeria. More so, to maintain and sustain exchange rate and economic stability. In the same vein, the government should pay more attention to other more volatile macroeconomic variables like oil price and the inflation rate in Nigeria.

Ismaila (2016) examined exchange rate depreciation and Nigerian economic performance after structural adjustment programmes (SAPs). The premise of the study was to examine exchange rate depreciation and Nigeria's economic growth during the SAP and post SAP period. The study covers the period of 1986–2012, using the Johansen co-integration test and error correction model analyses. The results show that a broad money supply, net export, and total government expenditure, have significant impacts on real output performance in the long run, while exchange rate has a direct and insignificant effect on Nigeria's economic growth in both the short and long run. This implies that exchange rate depreciation during the SAP period has no robust effect on Nigeria's economic performance. Therefore, the author suggested that policy makers should not totally rely on the exchange rate depreciation policy instrument to induce economic growth, but should use it to complement other macro-economic policies such as monetary and fiscal policies.

Adeniran, Yusuf, and Adeyemi (2014) investigated the impact of exchange rate fluctuation on the Nigerian economic growth from 1986, being the year the monetary authority shifted from the fixed exchange rate regime to a flexible exchange rate regime, to 2013. The ordinary least square (OLS) was used to analyse the data. The result revealed that the exchange rate has a

positive impact but not significant with ($\beta = 0.014$, $t = 1.783$, Pns) thus affirming previous studies that developing countries are relatively better off in their choice of flexible exchange rate regimes. The result also indicated that the interest rate and rate of inflation have negative impacts on economic growth, but these are not significant. Therefore, the authors recommended that government should encourage the export promotion strategies in order to maintain a surplus balance of trade and also conducive environment, adequate security, effective fiscal and monetary, as well as infrastructural facilities should be provided so that foreign investors will be attracted to invest in Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

To actualise the objectives of this study, the ordinary least square (OLS) estimation technique will be employed.

The methodology of this study follows the framework of growth accounting Cobb-Douglas production function embedded in the Solow residual growth model. This model however tries to incorporate the technological process into the Cobb-Douglas production function which could be referred to as total factor productivity or TFP (A). It is however derived as such suppose we want to estimate the contribution of inputs and productivity changes to output. This approach is known as growth accounting.

We start with a production function that states that output Y is produced by inputs of capital (K) and labour (L), and by the economy's level of total factor productivity or TFP (A). Using a Cobb-Douglas production function:

$$Y = A K^{\alpha} L^{1-\alpha} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

If output changes, then it must be because of changes in capital or labour, or advances in total factor productivity. Therefore, an economy can grow via factor accumulation, which refers to increasing the inputs of labour and capital, or by increases in total factor productivity, which refers to productivity advances or technological progress. The former would lead to

an increase in the level of growth, if it were, say investment in the neoclassical model, while the latter could generate an increase in the rate of economic growth. Computing the different contributions of K, L, and A to output growth is known as a growth accounting exercise.

The technology variable can be viewed as labour augmenting meaning that a unit of labour is more productive when the level of technology is higher. This is shown in the equation below:

$$Y = F(K, AL) = K^\alpha (AL)^{1-\alpha} \dots\dots\dots (2a)$$

Similarly, the technology variable can be viewed as capital augmenting, meaning that a unit of capital is more productive when the level of technology is higher. This is also shown in the equation below.

$$Y = F(AK, L) = (AK)^\alpha L^{1-\alpha} \dots\dots\dots (2b)$$

The above equations (2a & 2b) holds in a Cobb-Douglas form for the production function where there is zero cross-price elasticity, and also on the assumption that technology (A) in the model is exogenously determined.

So, what economists do when they try to account for growth is that they first measure the contribution to output of capital and labour. What will be left is often called ‘Solow residual’. This is the unexplained portion of output that is not attributable to the measured inputs and is thought to be a measure of TFP (A).

Criticism levied at this approach argues that the Solow residual is not a measure of technology, but picks up ‘shocks’ in the economy, such as monetary shocks or military spending, for example. Essentially, the critique is that the Solow residual just captures growth that is not explained by the growth in inputs because of measurement problems, and therefore, we cannot assume that these are productivity advances.

It is worthy of note that technological progress determines whether continuing growth is possible or not. This technical condition has to do with

the substitutability of renewable and non-renewable resources and the initial endowment of capital and natural resources and the ease of substitution among inputs.

3.1 Theoretical framework and model specification

This study follows the framework of growth accounting according to the Cobb-Douglas production function. And it specifically adopts the model used by Omran and Bolbol (2003) to explain the effects of exchange rate fluctuations and oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria.

$$PCYG = a + b_1R + b_2T + b_3C + e \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:

R = Vector of variables that are generally recognised to explain growth (e.g. initial per capital income, human capital, investment, exchange rate fluctuations, oil revenue etc.)

T = Vector of variables that under study are presumed to affect growth

C = Vector of selected variables usually used as control in estimating growth (e.g. foreign direct investment)

e = White noise

It is important to provide an explicit mathematical treatment of the inclusion of the interaction variables under study. The focus is to modify the equation (1) based on the accounting framework of the Cobb-Douglas production function, and then estimate it in order to account for the interaction variables.

$$Y = AL^\alpha K^\beta \dots\dots\dots (1.1)$$

$$A = F(E_r, O_r) \dots\dots\dots (1.2)$$

Combining equations 1.1 and 1.2 we have;

$$Y = A(E_r, O_r) L^\alpha K^\beta \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

- Y = Output
- A = Total factor productivity (TFP)
- E_r = Exchange rate fluctuation
- O_r = Oil revenue
- L = Labour
- K = Capital

Taking the Log differential of equation 2, we have

$$\hat{Y} = A' (E_r.dO_r + O_r.dE_r) / A + \alpha \hat{L} + \beta \hat{K} \dots (3)$$

Where;

A' = Derivation of A with respect to the interaction between E_r.O_r

dE_r = Exchange rate fluctuation.

Let A' Y/A = λ, then

$$A' Y/A = \lambda \dots \dots \dots (3.1)$$

Making A subject of formula in equation 3.1 we have:

$$A = A' Y / \lambda \dots \dots \dots (3.2)$$

Substituting equation 3.2 into equation 3 we have:

$$\hat{Y} = \lambda.(E_r.dO_r)/Y + \lambda.(O_r.dE_r)/Y + \alpha \hat{L} + \beta \hat{K} \dots (4)$$

The term O_r.dE_r/Y, in equation 4 captures the relationship between oil revenue and the exchange rate fluctuation ratio. Also, equation 4 can be transformed from a growth accounting equation to a growth equation in estimable functional form and this is only possible if K is proxied by investment ratio I/GDP while λ.(E_r.dO_r)/Y is designated as constant and PCYG is plausibly substituted for growth in Y/L. Taking initial per capital income (PCY), E_r, O_r and investment ratio as the elements in vector R.

$$PCYG = a + b_{11}IPCY + b_{12}Or/GDP + b_{13}I/GDP + b_{14}E_r + b_{2}E_r.O_r/GDP + b_{3}C + e..... (5)$$

Where:

PCYG = per capital income growth

IPCY = initial per capital income

I = investment proxied by gross fixed capital formation

C = Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

GDP = gross domestic product

b₁₁- b₁₄, b₂ and b₃ = coefficients of the independent variables

Equation (5) will be estimated for different successive models in order to capture all the vector of independent variables with the use of Ordinary Least Square regression estimates and the results will be presented and discussed in the next section of this study.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis began with an examination of trends for our variables of interest viz: Oil Revenue, Exchange Rate and GDP Growth Rate in Nigeria. The data for oil revenue and exchange rate for the period of study were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) bulletin and the data for (GDP) Growth Rate, per capita income and investment were obtained from the World Development Indicators. The trends for our variables are however shown below;

4.1 Trend of oil revenue

Source: Author's computation (2017)

Figure 1 shows oil revenue from 1981-1998 was low and this was as a result of low prices for crude oil in the international market. From 1999-2009 it was fluctuating till 2009 when it increased continuously and by 2011 it has reached its all-time maximum of 8878.97 billion naira and thereafter declined drastically up to 2015 on account of the fact that the USA that used to import crude oil from Nigeria, stopped buying and started selling, resulting in a decline in oil revenue.

4.2 Trend of exchange rate

Source: Author's computation (2017)

Figure 2 shows that from 1981-1985 the naira was more valuable than the dollar. Then it started depreciating at a slow rate from 1986-1998, which could be attributed to the implementation of the structural adjustment program during the period under discussion. From 1989 onwards it kept on depreciating continuously, till it reached its maximum in 2015 at #193.28 naira to a dollar.

4.3 Trend of per capital income growth

Figure 3 Graphical trend of per capital income growth in Nigeria from 1981-2015

Source: Author's computation (2017)

Figure 3 shows that per capital income growth in Nigeria has been very volatile over the period of the study, with its highest minimum being a negative of 15 in 1981, and an all-time maximum of 30 in 2004 and declining from 2005 to 2015.

4.4 Descriptive statistics

Table 1: Descriptive statistics on all variables of interest

	GDP	FDI	ER	I	IPCY	PCYG	OR
Mean	20133.50	326.5212	71.53803	12.58818	1639.797	1.024532	2197.071
Median	4588.990	110.4527	22.05110	11.74670	1405.892	1.508833	416.8100
Maximum	94144.96	1360.308	193.2792	34.02084	2548.427	30.34224	8878.970
Minimum	144.8312	0.264300	0.610000	5.467015	1147.073	-15.45826	7.250000
Std. Dev.	28608.18	422.5601	66.29919	6.122224	462.0091	7.475821	2753.057
Skewness	1.398183	1.093160	0.225439	1.837585	0.814355	1.175230	1.006505
Kurtosis	3.630694	2.812109	1.350634	6.809332	2.109619	8.631681	2.646691
Jarque-Bera	11.98377	7.022307	4.263730	40.85941	5.024648	54.30905	6.091507
Probability	0.002499	0.029862	0.118616	0.000000	0.081080	0.000000	0.047560
Sum	704672.3	11428.24	2503.831	440.5864	57392.90	35.85862	76897.48
SumSq. Dev.	2.78E+10	6070939.	149449.8	1274.375	7257382.	1900.188	2.58E+08
Observations	35	35	35	35	35	35	35

Source: Author's computation (2017)

Table 1 represents descriptive statistics on all variables of interest. The mean value of the exchange rate is N71.53803 with a maximum of 193.2792, and a minimum of 0.61, which shows that the naira was once more valuable than US dollars. The dispersion of the exchange rate from the mean stands at 66.29919, showing that the exchange rate is highly volatile and depreciates constantly. Oil revenue in Nigeria has a mean value of N 2197.071, with a maximum and minimum of N 8878.970 billion and N 7.250000 respectively. The high maximum value has been as a result of an increase in the international price of crude oil especially between 2009-2011, and also as a result of increased investment and activities in the oil sector, hence generating a substantial amount of revenue for the Nigerian government. In Nigeria, the per capital income growth have been significantly low with an average value of 1.024532, with a maximum of 30.34224 and crashes to the

negative minimum of 15.45826, while the dispersion from the mean value stands at 7.475821.

The skewness statistic from the table 1 revealed that all the variables used are positively skewed. The Jarque-Bera statistic rejected the null hypothesis of normal distribution for all the variables - gross domestic product (GDP), foreign direct investment (FDI), investment in fixed capital (I), oil revenue (OR) and per capital income growth (PCYG) at five percent critical value with exception to exchange rate (ER) and initial per capital income (IPCY). For exchange rate and initial per capital income, the Jarque-Bera statistic could not reject the null hypothesis of normal distribution for the variables at five percent critical value.

4.5 Unit root test of variables

Unit root test was also conducted via the Augmented Dicky-Fuller and Philips Perron tests, the variables were either stationary at level or first difference as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Unit root test

VARIABLE	ADF		PP		Order of Integration
	Level	1 st Diff	Level	1 st Diff	
ER	0.330948 (0.9766)	-5.196931 (0.0002)*	0.338134 (0.9770)	-5.194520 (0.0002)**	I(1)
GDP	-3.245753 (0.0270)**	-0.445281 (0.8892)	6.847477 (1.0000)	-1.217166 (0.6551)	I(0)
FDI	-6.490766 (0.0000)*	-3.911110 (0.0063)*	-1.184173 (0.6698)	-7.046377 (0.0000)**	I(1)
PCYG	-4.824558 (0.0004)*	-8.685686 (0.0000)*	-4.819018 (0.0004)*	-21.18823 (0.0001)*	I(1)
IPCY	0.986308 (0.9955)	-4.288065 (0.0019)*	0.587055 (0.9873)	-4.246477 (0.0021)**	I(1)
OR	-1.336717 (0.6010)	-1.560351 (0.4873)	-1.227494 (0.6510)	-6.059003 (0.0000)**	I(1)
I	-4.447056 (0.0012)*	-5.030075 (0.0003)*	-4.447056 (0.0012)*	-4.447056 (0.0012)**	I(1)

Source: Author's computation (2017) *stationary at 1%, **stationary at 5% level of significance

4.6 Ordinary least square result

Table 3: Ordinary least square result

Dependent Variable PCYG		
Independent Variable	Model 1	Model 2
C	-18.31(-1.97)***	-16.06(-1.77)***
IPCY	0.01(1.79)***	0.02(2.33)**
I/GDP	-64.76(-2.36)**	-93.28(-2.99)*
OR/GDP	47.35(1.84)***	-19.63(0.67)
ER	-0.003(-0.071978)	-0.09(-1.41)
FDI	-0.01(-1.72)***	-0.01(-2.21)**
ER*(OR/GDP)		0.72(1.72)***
N	35	35
R ² (%)	43	48
F-stat	4.32*	4.34*
DW	1.84	1.93

Source: Author's computation (2017). Figures in bracket are t-statistics *, **, *** significant at 1%, 5% & 10% respectively.

From Table 3, model 1 is the regression model without the inclusion of the interaction term between ER & OR ratio, while model 2 is the regression model with the inclusion of the interaction term.

From model 1, the constant (C) given as -18.31, which is statistically significant at 10% and shows that the dependent variable (PCYG) will decrease by 18.31 if all the independent variables are held constant therefore, signifying a decline in the standard of living. The initial per capital income

(IPCY) is directly related to the dependent variable PCYG on account of its coefficient, which is 0.01, depicting a unit increase in IPCY and will result in an increase in the dependent variable PCYG by 0.01. Similarly, the coefficient of OR/GDP is 47.35, showing that there is a positive relationship between oil revenue ratio to GDP & PCYG i.e., a unit increase in the OR ratio will cause PCYG to increase by 47.35. This therefore conforms to a prior expectation and is statistically significant at 10% level of significance. Also, the coefficient of ER is -0.003, implying an increase in ER (depreciation of naira) by 1 unit will result in a decline in PCYG by 0.03, but this result was however statistically insignificant. Also, the coefficient of FDI is -0.01 showing an inverse relationship between FDI and the explained variable. This does not however conform to a prior expectation, even though it's statistically significant at 10% level of significance. The negative value of the independent variable (FDI) could be as a result of political instability and corruption, as funds that should have been invested in the economy are been diverted into the pockets of a few individuals, hence the reason for its negative value. The R^2 , which is 43%, shows that the explanatory variables have been able to successfully explain 43% of the total change in the explained variable. The Durbin-Watson statistic, which is 1.84, shows there is an absence of autocorrelation in the model, while the F-statistics which is significant at 1% level of significance shows that the entire model is statistically reliable.

Upon the inclusion of the interaction term between ER & OR ratio in model 2, the result became more statistically significant and robust. The coefficient of IPCY increased to 0.02 and became statistically significant at 5% compared to 10% in model 1. Similarly, ER coefficient became -0.09, but remained statistically insignificant as in model 1. Also, the coefficient of OR ratio became negative, although it was statistically insignificant. The coefficient of FDI remained the same, but became statistically significant at 5%. The interaction term between ER & OR ratio, which was included in model 2, has a coefficient of 0.72 showing a direct and positive relationship between the interaction term ER & OR ratio and the explained variable

PCYG and is statistically significant validating as a result the main hypothesis of the study. The R^2 improved from 43% in model 1 to 48% in model 2, and so did the Durbin-Watson statistic improve from 1.84 to 1.93, upon the inclusion of the interaction term between ER & OR ratio in model 2.

It is also interesting to find the threshold level beyond which ER interacted with OR will affect PCYG negatively. This can be obtained from model 2 by differentiating GDP with respect to OR ratio and setting the derivative equal to zero.

$$-19.63 + 0.72ER = 0 \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

From equation 6,

$$ER = \frac{19.63}{0.72} = 27.3\%$$

ER 27.3% is therefore the desired threshold level. This positive value of the interaction coefficient reveals the true nature of the relationship between ER & OR on economic growth in Nigeria. It therefore suggests a complementary role in economic growth i.e. as oil revenue is increasing, exchange rate is appreciating. One simple justification for the finding may be because as oil revenue increases on account of the increase in the international price of crude oil, the demand for naira in the foreign exchange market increases, hence an appreciation in the exchange rate, since crude oil serves as Nigeria's major source of foreign exchange earnings due to failure of the government to diversify the economy. Similarly, a decline in oil revenue on account of a decrease in the international price of crude oil implies less demand for naira in the foreign exchange market and hence, a depreciation in the exchange rate.

Finally, the value of the R^2 , which is 48% in model 2, shows that the dependent variable PCYG is being affected by other variable(s) which the researcher did not consider in the course of this research. Hence there is need for further research in other to account for these variable(s).

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Existing literature has failed to empirically examine the joint impact of exchange rate fluctuation and oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. This analysis was motivated by the fact that the Nigerian economy depends heavily on crude oil serving as the major source of government revenue and volatility in its prices has, and still significantly, affects major economic variables. This study therefore examined the empirical relationship between oil revenue and exchange rate fluctuation, as well as the impact of their interaction on economic growth in Nigeria. It was concluded from the findings of this study that ER was negative and statistically insignificant (on its own), the OR ratio is positive and statistically significant (in model 1), and the interaction between ER and OR ratio is positive and statistically significant. Given the positive value of the interaction variables, the study concludes that oil revenue and exchange rate fluctuation play a complementary role in affecting economic growth in Nigeria and that exchange rate is constrained by oil revenue in Nigeria and unless this situation is improved, substantial exchange rate appreciation may not be achieved in Nigeria.

5.1 Policy recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the researcher makes the following recommendations:

- The country should diversify its export revenue base as a means of minimising reliance on crude oil and petroleum products. This will further shield the economy from extreme declines in government revenue due to the volatility of the crude oil price in the international market.
- Since there is a the complementary role of oil revenue and the exchange rate there is need for government to invest in the oil sector through the construction of new refineries and the repair of the existing refineries in order to increase oil revenue through increased

exports thereby increasing the demand for naira in the foreign exchange market and hence an appreciation in exchange rate.

- Moreover, adequate measures should be put in place to de-link the complementary movements of the naira exchange rate from oil revenue due to oil price changes through the diversification of the economy. This is because oil prices are highly volatile and very unsettled. If current vagaries in the prices of oil categorically affect exchange rate, then long run stability of the external sector is not assured.
- Exchange rate stability could therefore be achieved, even in the face of dwindling oil revenues, through conscious efforts aimed at infrastructural development and diversification of the export-base of the economy, increasing Nigeria foreign exchange earnings and therefore reducing the proportion of crude oil contribution to foreign exchange earnings thus, reducing stocks on the exchange rate from falls in the oil price in the international market.

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